
KEY PRINCIPLES OF FORMING A HEALTHY LIFESTYLE

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Abstract: the article deals with the philosophical approach to the formation of a healthy lifestyle based on the integration of various cultural and philosophical traditions. Emphasis is placed on holistic approach, awareness, ethical aspects and social significance of health. It is emphasised that health is a harmony of body, mind and spirit achieved through a balanced lifestyle. Practical recommendations are given and the significance of philosophical understanding of health for modern culture is revealed.

Key words: healthy lifestyle, philosophy of health, holistic approach, awareness, harmony, health ethics.

Аннотация: в статье рассматривается философский подход к формированию здорового образа жизни, основанный на интеграции различных культурных и философских традиций. Акцент сделан на холистическом подходе, осознанности, этических аспектах и социальной значимости здоровья. Подчеркивается, что здоровье – это гармония тела, разума и духа, достигнутая через сбалансированный образ жизни. Приведены практические рекомендации и раскрыта значимость философского осмысления здоровья для современной культуры.

Ключевые слова: здоровый образ жизни, философия здоровья, холистический подход, осознанность, гармония, этика здоровья.

A healthy lifestyle, from a philosophical point of view, is a multifaceted and multivalent concept that goes beyond mere physical fitness. In philosophy, from ancient Greek thinkers to modern scientists, health has been regarded as harmony between body, mind and spirit. The principles of a healthy lifestyle address ethical, social and mental aspects, which allows us to look at health as a broader phenomenon than just the absence of disease.

From ancient Greek thinkers to Eastern philosophers, health has always been viewed through the lens of wholeness. The ancient Greek philosopher Socrates asserted that ‘know thyself’, emphasising the importance of self-awareness and understanding of one's own body and its needs[1]. Modern research confirms that attention to one's bodily state, proper nutrition, regular physical activity and inner peace form the basis of a healthy lifestyle.

The philosophical understanding of health is based on a holistic approach originating in ancient Eastern traditions. According to this approach, the human being is a holistic system where all aspects of health are interconnected. In Chinese philosophy, the balance of yin and yang is the key to health: disharmony of these forces leads to disease, while their balance ensures well-being, i.e. it emphasises the importance of harmonising opposing forces to achieve health. Indian Ayurveda offers the concept of three doshas - vata, pitta and kapha - whose harmony allows a person to achieve physical and emotional balance[2]. These approaches prove that health is impossible without taking into account the mental and spiritual components.

Modern studies in the field of psychosomatics, such as the works of G.S. Lazarev and V.A. Vorobyov, confirm that human health cannot be considered without taking into account its emotional state and psychological well-being. It is important to note that a healthy body requires not only physical activity and proper nutrition, but also a harmonious state of inner peace.

Western philosophy, since antiquity, has also emphasised a conscious approach to health. Philosophers such as Plato and Aristotle argued that humans are able to achieve harmony through the development of self-awareness and moral qualities[3][4]. The word ‘mindfulness’ has become a key concept in recent decades in both the fields of psychology and health philosophy.

Modern health philosophy integrates these ideas and emphasises the importance of developing body awareness. Cultivating mindfulness in relation to nutrition, physical activity and psycho-emotional well-being promotes a more balanced and harmonious lifestyle. The work of scientists such as Jon Kabat-Zinn (author of the concept of mindfulness) confirms that being mindful of daily habits and the world around us has a profound effect on our overall health[5].

The philosophy of health is inextricably linked to ethical principles, which serve as the basis for the formation of healthy habits and ethics of life. The most important of these principles is responsibility. Responsibility to oneself and society for maintaining health includes such important aspects as being aware of one's needs and limitations, paying attention to one's bodily condition and exercising moderation in various areas of life.

The principle of moderation, which originated in ancient Greek philosophy, particularly in the teachings of Aristotle, states that excess in any area of life - be it food, labour or leisure - leads to imbalance and disease. In the modern context, philosophers of health, such as T. Higgins and L. Greenberg, emphasise that the key element of a healthy lifestyle is balance and the capacity not only for physical but also for psycho-emotional balance[6].

Modern philosophical thought emphasises the social nature of health. Healthy lifestyles are seen not only as individual choices but also as social practices. The

complexity and importance of social ties, including mutual support, the ability to work in teams and socialise with others, also influence the maintenance of health. The works of modern philosophers, such as M. Foucault and A. Giddens, emphasise that the social conditions in which a person lives create or hinder the possibility of forming healthy habits[7]. In the context of modern realities, this means creating an environment conducive to physical, mental and social well-being.

Based on the philosophical understanding of the studies I have analysed, it is possible to identify several key principles of forming a healthy lifestyle.

Firstly, it is the principle of integrity, which integrates physical, mental and spiritual health;

Secondly, mindfulness - attention and self-awareness in relations with oneself and the surrounding world;

Third, moderation and balance in all aspects of life, from nutrition to emotional activity.

The principle of naturalness implies following the natural rhythms and needs of the body, which is associated with awareness of one's biological cycles and

limitations. It is important that health maintenance becomes a systematic process, where each day includes successive steps towards harmony.

A philosophical approach to wellness offers a holistic understanding of health as a multidimensional phenomenon. The integration of various cultural and philosophical traditions allows for the creation of a system of principles that promote not only physical health, but also general human well-being. The philosophy of health goes beyond simple rules and recommendations, offering a conscious way of development leading to harmony with oneself and the world around. It is a continuous process of self-discovery and self-improvement based on the wisdom accumulated by mankind over millennia.

A healthy lifestyle, from a philosophical point of view, is not an end goal, but a continuous process orientated towards the development of inner harmony and awareness. These values, despite different cultural contexts, remain universal and relevant in today's world.

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